

A Green ICASSP 2020 in Virtual Barcelona

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One of our goals when we started to organize ICASSP in Barcelona was to promote an environmentally conscious conference, trying to reduce the use of paper, recycling plastic badges, replacing USB proceedings with electronic downloads and promoting the use of electronic tools as an alternative to the conference booklet. Now that the conference is over, we can say that we promised a green ICASSP and we certainly delivered!

It goes without saying that the conference we had originally planned for was quite different from what it eventually turned out to be. In fact, our plans for ICASSP were continuously evolving according to a rapidly changing reality dictated by a pandemic that moved forward beyond the imaginable. At the beginning, there was a common belief that the pandemic would only affect some geographical areas of the globe, so our efforts were devoted to identifying the mostly affected sessions and moving them physically to an area of the conference venue that would permit remote presentations. At one point, we even tried to hire LCD screens for remote paper presentations and included a pair of Bluetooth earbuds as part of the registration package in order to have virtual poster sessions. Unfortunately, seven weeks before the conference started, we had to make the difficult decision of moving the conference to a fully virtual event.

Judging by the current numbers, ICASSP'2020 has been a tremendous success. The total number of registrants is now over 16,000, which is more than five times the highest number of registrants that ICASSP has ever had! Also, our 18 industry sponsors have been extremely supportive. This has created a great opportunity not only for academic interaction, but also for participating in the diverse industry activities.

This conference has been the result of a team work, and this has been a wonderful experience. We have realized and sensed that there is an alive SPS community, active and supportive. The Technical Program Chairs, Markus Rupp, Christian Jutten and Pascale Fung have been proactive from day zero and key to build the foundations of ICASSP'2020. We thank them and also the whole organizing committee, and IEEE SPS staff, who incredibly teamed up in the last mile, when we decided to go fully virtual. Without them, this conference would not have been a

reality. The result has been a colorful program that offered a wide range of activities, and which content has been available one month after the end of the conference in May (i.e., available till June 8th).

I. CONFERENCE PROGRAM HIGHLIGHTS

ICASSP'2020 came with an excellent program, with five amazing plenary speakers that generated a lot of expectation and an amazingly high turnout at their live virtual sessions: “From compressed sensing to deep learning: tasks, structures, and models” by Yonina Eldar, “Deep Representation Learning” by Yoshua Bengio, “Gauss-Fourier-Wiener-Kalman Ensembles for Adaptivity and Robustness” by Georgios Giannakis, “Multiantenna Precoding in Wireless Communication Systems” by Björn Ottersten and “Conversational Systems and the Marriage of Speech and Language” by Mari Ostendorf. Thank you all for all these amazing talks!

We also followed the lead of the organizers of the Brighton's edition and included a series of nine Expert-To-Non-Expert (ETON) talks throughout the conference. We were aware that these talks had been very well received in the past, so we tried to allocate a higher number of those into the program. As for the scope of the talks, we tried to cover current hot topics -namely: distributed machine learning for comms (D. Gunduz), decentralized learning (M. Rabbat), challenges in sound and music computing (X. Serra) or nonlinear MMSE in compressed sensing and Kalman filtering (D. Slock)- with some additional different subjects that fall slightly beyond the current scope of conventional signal processing: molecular storage and computing (O. Milenkovic), quantum information processing (E. Soljanin), challenges in opportunistic weather monitoring (H. Messer), biosignal-based spoken communication (T. Schultz) or the blockchain trilemma (D. Tse). The help of the special session chairs was fundamental in order to select and organize these talks. One of the most important novelties of the technical program with respect to previous editions of ICASSP was the introduction of an industrial track, chaired by Fa-Long Luo. This program included three invited speaker sessions on current hot topics of high industrial relevance, namely a session on signal processing for IoT and DataNet, a session on computational sensing and vision technology, and a session on smart sound and voice processing for the digital society. This was complemented with three industry panel sessions on different aspects of current relevance in the signal processing industry, including a panel on “The B5G/6G Challenge – A Race of Enabling Technologies and Design Principle” (organized by A. Alexiou and participated by R. Valenzuela, P. Popovski, J. Jornet, M. Debbah and M. Juntti), a panel on

“Signal Processing for Integrated Terrestrial, Airborne and Satellite Networks” (organized by J. Grotz and participated by A. Khayrallah, J. Wigard, E. Callejo Luis, A. Franchi, O. Liberg and O. Vidal), and a panel on “Signal Processing for Extended Reality” (organized by G. Hernandez Abrego and participated by D. Filip, I. Tashev, R. Mehra, E. Murphy-Chutorian and A. Peck). In parallel with this, we also had four industrial keynote speakers that explored a number of hot topics in industrial applications of signal processing, going from the connections between speech and finance AI (L. Deng), 6G networks (P. Zhu), radar applications (A. Farina) or the value of technical standards (E. Au). The above live industrial program was complemented with 27 Show and Tell Demo presentations offered on demand, which generated a lot of interest, judging from the high number of page visits they received.

In parallel with the industrial track, we offered five workshops, three of them organized by our diamond patrons (Amazon, Sony and Huawei), another one by our silver patron Mathworks and finally the traditional SPS-organized interactive workshop for Young Professionals, which this year was devoted to the use of social media as tools for the scientist. Other SPS-organized events were adapted to the virtual format, such as the Women in Signal Processing event (which this year changed format and featured a very interesting talk by L. Duro on radioactive waste management), the SPCup competition (which was offered as a live event), or a novel activity entitled SPS 5-Minute Video Clip Contest (which featured several teams creating a video that would disseminate signal processing topics -this year, beamforming- to a wider audience).

Another important novelty of the ICASSP’2020 program was the inclusion of two specific Collaborative Sessions in Data Science, initiated by T. Adali and P. Schreier, which consisted of papers originally submitted to multiple technical tracks with a common flavor on data science, which honored our motto “Signal Processing: from Sensors to Information, at the Heart of Data Science”. In particular, two collaborative sessions were organized, the first one dealing with highly complex, heterogeneous and high-dimensional data and the second one on robustness, reproducibility and replicability. These sessions had a significant number of virtual attendees, which confirmed the interest of our audience in data science topics. Judging by the results, collaboration between different technical committees is highly recommended in future editions of the conference.

We also continued the longstanding tradition of ICASSP in offering a set of 11 high quality tutorials. These were extremely well received, since preliminary statistics indicate that almost half of the total live event views during the whole conference (according to Zoom reports) was at

one of these tutorials. These tutorials are available ondemand from now on, first at the conference platform and then afterwards at the SPS resource center, so do not miss the chance to watch them again! Topics include: Machine Learning and Wireless Communications (Y. Eldar, V. Poor and N. Shlezinger), Distributed and Efficient Deep Learning (W. Samek and F. Sattler), Graph Filters with Applications to Distributed Optimization and Neural Networks (G. Leus, E. Isufi and M. Coutino), Quantum Signal Processing and Communications – a Glimpse beyond Moore’s Law (L. Hanzo, A. Sera Cacciapuoti and M. Caleffi), Robust Data Science: Modern Tools for Detection, Clustering and Cluster Enumeration (M. Fauß, M. Muma and A. M. Zoubir), Signal Processing for MIMO Communications Beyond 5G (E. Björnson and J. Zhang), Adversarial Robustness of Deep Learning Models: Attack, Defense and Verification (P.-Y. Chen), Graph Neural Networks (A. Ribeiro and F. Gama), Biomedical Image Reconstruction—From Foundations to Deep Neural Networks, Game theoretic learning and applications to spectrum collaboration (A. Leshem and K. Cohen) and Information Extraction in Joint Millimeter-Wave State Sensing and Communications: Fundamentals to Applications (K. V. Mishra, B. Shankar and M. Kobayashi).

Finally, one regular and two student best papers were awarded at ICASSP’2020. These awards were managed by two ad-hoc committees, which required some preliminary tasks to area Technical Chairs (TC) and involved the TPC, student chairs and special sessions chairs.

II. PAPER STATISTICS AND REVIEW PROCESS

The number of paper submissions to ICASSP’2020 experimented a substantial increase with respect to the previous editions. A total of 3,939 papers were submitted to regular sessions (leaving journal presentations aside), out of which 1,922 were accepted for presentation during the conference (47.2% acceptance ratio). This was around a 12% increase in the number of submissions with respect to the previous edition of ICASSP. As Figure 1, most of the accepted papers came from the United States (24%), China (21%), France (6%), Japan (6%), Germany (5%) and United Kingdom (4%). The paper tracks with most accepted papers were the Speech Processing track (20%) and the Machine Learning track (13%).

In this year’s edition we followed the trend initiated in Brighton and accepted a relatively high number of special sessions (30). In order to handle such an increased number of special session papers, we tried to involve the technical committees in the paper decision process. Each special session paper had two different types of reviewers: some reviewers appointed by the session organizers, and some additional reviewers appointed by the technical committees. This

Fig. 1. Number of accepted papers per country

mixed review process guaranteed that the technical quality of the accepted papers was fully in line with the rest of the conference while ensuring that these papers were being reviewed by competent scientists, with backgrounds close to their domain of application.

The review process of the regular papers was conducted by a huge workforce of 2,471 reviewers, to them our honest gratitude! While most of the reviewers carried out a reasonable number of reviews (between 1 and 5), almost half of the reviews felt upon a small group of volunteers with a much higher review load. More specifically, around 48% of the papers were reviewed by volunteers that had to submit their recommendations on 6 to 15 papers. This is something that we should all try to equalize in future events, since we believe it would be more desirable that all reviewers shared approximately the same workload.

III. CHOOSING A VIRTUAL PLATFORM

One of the biggest issues of the whole process was to choose the platform that would host the virtual conference. Given the technical complexity of the program, together with the extremely

tight schedule leading up to the conference, we decided from the very beginning that the main part of the technical program would be available on-demand in the form of video presentation recordings with some offline Question and Answer (Q&A) forum.

ICASSP has always regarded poster and lecture sessions as being of the same technical quality. It made sense that both types of presentations were offered the same possibilities on the virtual platform. For this reason, we decided to have them all as 15 min video presentations, irrespective of whether the original presentation format assigned to the paper was a lecture or a poster.

The choice of a virtual conference platform was made with three strong requirements in mind: (i) the content should be available all over the world; (ii) we needed a full integration with the company that implemented all the technical program, which meant that the two teams had to work hand-in-hand to achieve a complete migration; (iii) most importantly, everything had to be done in a very short period time, since we had only a few weeks before the conference started. Here, once again, the help of the SPS team was the key to the success, and we will always be indebted for their help at these times.

IV. NEW CONFERENCE STRUCTURE

With the short notice lockdown, we had to make fast decisions and one of the first ones was to stick to the planned dates and keep the program as we had originally drawn it up for the onsite event. The technical program was completely finalized and by following the original scheduled we could also capture, as much as possible, the feeling of the conference and the sense that many attendees were simultaneously present. However, as we have already commented, we had to re-structure the conference as not all activities could go live. Therefore, we developed two parallel paths: the live program and the on-demand sessions.

The live program was devoted to the special activities, such as: tutorials, opening ceremony, keynote talks, ETON talks, industry panels, woman in signal processing forum, patron's workshops, young professional's workshop, student job fair, social and cultural meet-ups, President's Town Hall and awards ceremony. All these activities were scheduled following Central European Summer Time CEST (GMT+2), that is Barcelona's time zone, and were available at the ICASSP'2020 virtual platform once they had taken place. Live program meant live Q&A forum and presentation (this latter depending on the speaker availability). To maximize the time zone range compatibility for live viewing around the globe, the main talks were scheduled in the afternoon CEST. The regular and special sessions (either oral or poster), together with the

Show and Tell demos, were pre-recorded and offered in the ondemand path. They were released at 8:00am CEST of the day where they are programmed. Due to going fully virtual, various other conference aspects changed. First, we decided to make the conference open for everyone, including non-authors. In this way we took the opportunity that the virtual platform offered to maximize the visibility, participation and impact of the conference. The proceedings were also open access for one month and a half, instead of the usual one month. Our motto was to be flexible, inclusive and global.

Second, the choice of Zoom meetings that was offered by the virtual platform proved to be a good decision as it allowed for a good management of speakers and audience. It also allowed either prerecorded or live presentations, and both showed high number of page views (posters: 120, 139, lectures: 70, 944, live program: 53, 352, social-cultural: 4, 749, with an average time on page of 2 minutes). Figure 2 shows more details. Scaling a fully live approach would have been possible had we had more time than barely one month to carry out the whole transition. This is because, among other things, rehearsals with any participant in the live program turned out to be key to ensure a good experience, which is a third aspect that changed with respect to an onsite event. Fourth, a chat channel within Zoom and a written Q&A offered by the virtual platform were the main tool for discussion. In fact, the no-show policy and the role of the session chairs rely on the Q&A forums: authors were requested to upload a video presenting their paper and be available to answer the Q&A forum within a certain time frame as stated in the conference policies. The session chairs' role was to monitor this activity. Fifth, and very important to have a good interaction, is to foster that attendees should use their full complete name and email address when participating in the virtual conference.

During the preparation of the onsite ICASSP we put a lot of effort in attracting exhibitors and sponsors, and we succeed to commit the participation of 31 different companies. After the virtual meeting announcement 13 of them cancelled their participation and 18 important patrons remained, which was good news, but required additional effort to be accommodated in the online format. Mainly, we did not know how to accommodate their publicity expectations. The outcome was successful for them, with an unexpected attendance to their workshops and an amount of useful attendees data and statistics. All in all, the virtual conference resulted in a good marketplace for sponsors.

Finally, essential to communicate the new structure and features was the email, in advance and daily during the conference. Among other things it communicated the virtual tours that

Fig. 2. Comparative number of pageviews of the different sessions in the ondemand and in the live program (Zomm sessions).

show different pieces of Barcelona and Catalan culture: Sagrada Familia, Dali museum, Gaudi’s modernism... They gave a moving experience to those that attended these tours. Amazingly, they were organized one week before the conference started. When all of us were living as on a roller-coaster of a series of unforeseen events, working around and against the clock, someone pointed out ”what about having some social-cultural experience?,” and we did not have time to think it over and simply went for it... and it was a hit.

V. SOME OVERVIEW ANALYTICS

As we mentioned above, the total number of registrants (+16,000) surpassed all the expectations and represented more than five times the maximum number ever achieved at an ICASSP before. There is little doubt that the fact that registrations were offered free of charge had something to do with these figures, but it was nevertheless surprising to see that ICASSP generated such a huge wave of interest all over the world. More than 40% of the registrants were not IEEE members, a fact that indicated that going virtual substantially increased the visibility of

the conference. Besides, the number of student registrations increased to around 30% of the total, a substantial increase with respect to previous ICASSP editions (around 25% in ICASSP'2019). Clearly, offering free registrations lure a wider spectrum of students into the conference.

Fig. 3. Geographical distribution of the registrations.

Figure 3 shows the geographical distribution of the registrants, around 21% was based in the USA, 10% in China and 8% in India. It is somewhat surprising to see that China contributed to around 25% of the paper submissions and only 10% of the registrations, and the reason for this may well be time zone differences or quality of experience of the virtual platform. Perhaps the ICASSP survey that has been launched sheds some light into the reasons for this imbalance.

By the end of the conference the total number of pageviews and sessions were 543,743 and 79,461, respectively. Figure 4 plots the daily active sessions and pageviews, not only during the conference, but also two weeks after the conference, when the ondemand material and open preview papers were available. During these two weeks the number of active sessions and pageviews increases above 40%. In terms of participation in the different life program events with Zoom meetings, Figure 2 plots the number of pageviews for both the ondemand and the

life program (i.e., Zoom sessions), giving the details of their different activities.

Fig. 4. Daily active sessions and pageviews.

VI. SPONSORS

After the announcement on March 16th that ICASSP'2020 was moved to a fully virtual conference, SPS dropped the target of a 20% surplus and aimed at a break-even budget. By that date, the number of registered people was 2,219 and an immediate refund policy was created. After applying it to non-author registrations, a total of 1,267 authors remained to be refunded after the conference. No additional income was generated since the registration to the virtual conference was free.

One of the nicest surprises was the fact that almost all sponsors (especially the high tier ones) kept their financial support, and in some cases they even increased it! We cannot finish this column without expressing our deepest gratitude to all of them. Thanks to them ICASSP'2020 has been able to refund part of the registration fees to those authors that were covering a paper. They were extremely supportive during the most difficult times when we really needed them, they were always patient and understanding when the situation was most unclear. This ICASSP would never have happened without you. Thank you!

VII. LESSONS LEARNED

“A small event as tiny as a drop of a pin can change the direction of your entire life,”... well, at least that of ICASSP'2020. It has been a great opportunity to be creative and lead. Definitely, our SPS community will have to work on being innovative in the forthcoming conferences.

Concerning the virtual event that we have organized diverse aspects could be improved. It is true that, once the technical program is built, a virtual event requires less logistics and shorter development time (e.g., there is no catering to be organized, no gala dinner, no conference venue to negotiate with,...). However, one must not dismiss the time for testing the virtual platform. There are also important details that we did not foresee, such as introducing 10 to 15 minutes breaks between activities, considering tools that allow voting (e.g., sort of clicking Like in Facebook) for the different presentations, etc...

Concerning the technical content of the ICASSP that we organized this year, there were some innovations that worked well as we have commented in this article. The industrial track, the collaborative sessions on Data Science or the new format of WISP, are activities worth keeping in future ICASSP editions. Due to the accumulative innovations, ICASSP is getting bigger and more complex every year. The only way to manage it is with a big, well-organized and supportive team. For all the technical program aspects, the contributions and efficiency of the TC are essential for a conference of the ICASSP quality and size. They organize the review process and session design in their area. In order to interact with them in a fast and friendly way, the general chairs have to choose a qualified TPC team, and assign to them clear responsibilities: i) the pre-review process, and together with the technical committees, provide a first sketch of the program; ii) during the review to achieve a fair outcome; iii) the rebuttal process, and iv) the conference awards. Contributions and efficacy of TC chairs are also essential for a conference of the ICASSP size.

Finally, the team does not only consist of the organizing committee, but also of all the services that are outsourced. A friendly relationship with the Professional Service Organizers, the SPS staff, to mention a few, is key. We wholeheartedly, thank you all!